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EFFICIENT MECHANISM OF BIOMASS (GARDEN AND FRUIT WASTE) USING BUFFERING MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The large organic matter of solid waste such as garden and fruit waste offer great potential for biogas production. Anaerobic digestion of green waste-food waste mixture at thermophilic temperature range was carried out with the primary aim of investigating the effect of buffer (NaHCO_3) and waste type in the digestion process, in order to initiate the digestion process.

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is a process by which microorganisms break down biodegradable material in the absence of oxygen. Anaerobic digestion can be used to treat various organic wastes and recover bio-energy in the form of biogas, which consists mainly of CH_4 and CO_2 . A great option for improving yields of anaerobic digestion of solid wastes is the co-digestion of multiple substrates. Numerous studies demonstrate that using co-substrates in anaerobic digestion system improves the biogas yields due to positive synergisms established in the digestion medium and the supply of missing nutrients by the co-substrates. In addition, co digestion offers several possible ecological economical advantages. Recent research (published during the past three years) on this topic is reviewed in the current paper

There was a digester tank of capacity 20 litre for decomposition of cow dung slurry and fruit waste. Two chemicals that are Na_2CO_3 and NaOH was used to make the buffer solution. Urea was added to increase the production of biogas. The fruit waste is grinded properly in grinding machine so that the surface area of slurry is increased and material will easily decompose in short time. Physio-chemical parameters of these influent (on the starting day of digestion) and effluent slurries (after 30th day from starting) in terms of total solid, volatile solid, temperature, pH and Non volatile solid were tested.

Overall study reveals that ideal condition for the production of bio gas is that pH of influent slurry must be 6.8 which was obtain by using buffering chemicals and waste should be grinded properly so that they decompose easily. This work can solve the problems of kitchen waste management as well as bring the fulfilment of energy requirement in terms of Biogas and optimization of biogas.

The ultimate biogas was obtained from using chiku (Sapodilla in Spanish), papaya, banana, muskmelon and mango fruit wastes as substrate was used. NaHCO_3 was added further in order to improve the yield of CH_4 . The volume of the digester was 20 litres. The solid waste of 9kg was used which comprised of 5kg Cow dung, 2kg Fruit Waste, 2kg garden waste and 100 gm of NaHCO_3 . The remaining space in the digester was filled with water.

INTRODUCTION

This volume of biomass can be converted to an enormous amount of energy and raw materials. Agricultural biomass waste converted to energy can substantially displace fossil fuel, reduce emissions of greenhouse gases and provide renewable energy to some people in developing countries, which still lack access to electricity. As raw materials, biomass wastes have attractive potentials for large-scale industries and community-level enterprises. Biomass takes the form of residual stalks, straw, leaves, roots, husk, nut or seed shells, waste wood and animal husbandry waste. Widely available, renewable, and virtually free, waste biomass is an important resource.

With the global campaign to combat climate change, countries are now looking for alternative sources of energy to minimize green house gas (GHG) emissions. Aside from being carbon neutral, the use of biomass for energy reduces dependency on the consumption of fossil fuel; hence, contributing to energy security and climate change mitigation.

As a common practice, direct combustion of agricultural residue results in air pollution thereby posing risk to human and ecological health. Biomass is a renewable resource that causes problems when not used. The challenge, therefore, is to convert biomass as a resource for energy and other productive uses.

Anaerobic biodegradation of organic fraction of solid waste material takes place in the absence of oxygen and the presence of anaerobic micro organisms. Anaerobic digestion is the consequences of a series of metabolic interactions among various groups of microorganism. It occurs in three stages, hydrolysis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis ^[1]. The first group of microorganism secretes enzymes that hydrolyse polymeric materials to monomers such as glucose and amino acids. These are subsequently converted by second group acetogenic bacteria to higher volatile fatty acids, H_2 acetic acid. At the last stage, the third group of bacteria, methanogenic, converts H_2 , CO_2 and acetate to CH_4 . It has been reported ^[2] that food wastes from kitchens and restaurants and green wastes from gardens, parks and forest as well as paper, wood chips and stationeries are some of the organic matter targeted for recycling.

Food wastes are relatively wet and decompose rapidly^[3]. This may lead to high initial acid accumulation resulting in acid pH, thus necessitating the need for chemical buffer to ensure process stability. In comparison green wastes are relatively dry and decompose slowly and consequently with

less possibility of high initial acid accumulation. Anaerobic digestion of combined food and green wastes may enhance the degradation of green wastes while slowing the decomposition of kitchen wastes. In addition, green wastes may also serve as a bulking agent [4], thus resulting in a more stabilised and viscous anaerobic digestate. The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of buffer (NaHCO_3) addition and waste type in batch and thermophilic high solids anaerobic digestion (HSAD) of organic fraction of municipal solid waste. HSAD is reputed to be a suitable method of treating organic fraction of municipal solid waste for optimisation of energy recovery and digestate quality with no requirement for dewatering [5,6]

There are advantages in the use of biomass. Biomass is a renewable resource that has a steady and abundant supply, especially those biomass resources that are by-products of agricultural activity. Its use is carbon neutral, can displace fossil fuels, and helps reduce GHG emissions while closing the carbon cycle loop.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The laboratory simulated feedstock was a mixture of Fruit Wastes (FW) and Garden Wastes (GW). The FW was a blended mixture of papaya, orange, pineapple, mango, muskmelon, chikoo and banana. The GW was a combination of garden waste grass, leaves, flowers, shrubs, herbs and wood chips. The collected green waste components were pre-sorted to remove undesirable materials such as large items and inert materials and to allow more efficient digestion and better digestate quality. The green waste was sieved using 4 mm sieve and milled in a portable kitchen miller. The Anaerobic sludge (AS) seed was obtained from a mesophilic reactor treating wastewater.

Methods

All experiments have been performed in 20L batch digesters essentially made of plastic. A set of 1 digester have been used at a time for experimentation. The following parameters of biogas production were calculated using various equipments.

1. pH of the Sample
2. Temperature
3. Total solid
 - ✓ Total solid of inlet slurry.
 - ✓ Total solid of out let slurry.
4. Non volatile solid
 - ✓ Non volatile solid of inlet slurry.
 - ✓ Non volatile solid of outlet slurry.
4. Volume of gas

Experimental Setup

- A - Digester tank PET Bottle
- B - Gas pipe
- C - T valve
- D- Gas valve
- E- Butyl Rubber Tube R13

Work plan:-

Biogas Plant is settled as shown in the above picture. The digester tank is painted black. Due to the transparency of the digester tank light will penetrate into the tank. If the light penetrates in to the digester tank algae will be produced. Production of algae leads to the development of oxygen which makes the bacteria respire aerobically, thus the process in anaerobic. Due to anaerobic action methane gas will be produced and thus the temperature of the mixture will be maintained.

Later on in the 10 litre water we mix 50 grams buffering material i.e. NaHCO_3 . Fruit waste and garden waste of 2 Kg each is collected and is chopped into pieces. All the materials i.e. 5 Kg cow dung, 2 Kg Fruit waste, 2Kg Garden Waste, buffering material and 10 litre water is mixed well in the tub. After mixing the ingredients in the tub they are poured in the digester tank. This slurry is poured into the digester tank using funnel and a small amount of sample is kept for performing the test. The digester tank is made air tight with the help of sealants and is kept for 30 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After 30 days we see that our tube is filled with biogas completely and gas is burns with brown flame. Various parameters of inlet and outlet of slurry is as follows:-

Table 1: Variation of different parameter at inlet and outlet

Parameter	pH	Temperature	Total solid	Volatile solid	Non Volatile solid
Inlet	6.8	31°C	76.31%	80%	20%
Outlet	5.6	34°C	35.22%	77.40%	22.60%

Table 2: Experimental details/Observation

S.No.	Day	Sample appearance	Evolution of gas	Ignition of Gas	Smell	Volume of gas(in m ³)
1	1Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	0.835*
2	5Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	0.894
3	10day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	0.927
4	15 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	0.984
5	20 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	1.008
6	25 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of Digester is rise	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	1.037
7	30 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	Ignition with light brown flame	Smell is like CNG	1.043

*Use of 5% KOH Flammability of gas appears well

Fig.1 Volume of gas generated day by day

Figure: **Volume of gas(in m³)/ Days**

Figure: **Volume of Gas(In M³)/ Days In**

Table: Temperature

Table: pH

Biogas Material in %

CONCLUSION

The addition of buffer (NaHCO₃) based on total solids contents increased the biodegradability of organic fraction of solid waste. It increased the cumulative volume of biogas production and percentage volatile solids reduction in substrate. This research work also shows that Fruit Waste (FW), Garden Waste (GW) and anaerobic sludge seed produced the highest biogas production of 1.043

cc/gVS and volatile solids destruction with the best pH (5.6) stability. Also buffering effect is indicated in the case of Fruit Waste and Garden Waste.

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